

D7.1 Brand identity and guidelines

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Control sheet

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
5G-IANA	5G for Intelligent Automotive Network Applications
5G-PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CMYK	Cyan, Magenta, Yellow, and Key
DML	Distributed Machine Learning
EU	European Union
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
RGB	Red, Green, Blue
SME	Small Medium Enterprise
VNF	Virtualised Network Function
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

Development of the 5G-IANA branding and guidelines is part of Task 7.1 (Communication strategy and tools) of WP7 (Dissemination, exploitation, standardisation and liaison activities). This deliverable, D7.1 - Brand identity and guidelines, is intended to be a reference document on brand material and guidelines to be followed by the 5G-IANA consortium.

The deliverable describes the development of 5G-IANA project's branding and visual identity. It also provides clear guidelines on how to correctly use 5G-IANA's brand and visual identity elements: the brand of the project, its logo, the typography, and the templates, to ensure a coherent and efficient communication of the project and its results.

The deliverable consists of the following sections:

- First chapter, an **Introduction** to 5G-IANA project's concept and approach, and to the purpose of the deliverable.
- Second chapter, **5G-IANA brand**, presents the project's Brand and Visual Identity.
- Third chapter, **5G-IANA brand guidelines**, provides precise guidelines on how to use the project's brand elements.
- Fourth chapter, the **Conclusion**, summarises the whole deliverable and its scope.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. 5G-IANA concept and approach

5G-IANA aims at providing an open 5G experimentation platform, on top of which third party experimenters, i.e., Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in the Automotive-related 5G-PPP vertical will have the opportunity to develop, deploy and test their services. An Automotive Open Experimental Platform (AOEP) will be specified, as the whole set of hardware and software resources that provides the computational and communication/transport infrastructure as well as the management and orchestration components, coupled with an enhanced NetApp Toolkit tailored to the Automotive sector. 5G-IANA will expose to experimenters secured and standardized Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) for facilitating all the different steps towards the production stage of a new service. 5G-IANA will target different virtualization technologies integrating different Management and Orchestration (MANO) frameworks for enabling the deployment of the end-to-end network services across different domains (vehicles, road infrastructure, Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) nodes and cloud resources). 5G-IANA NetApp toolkit will be linked with a new Automotive Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) Repository including an extended list of ready to use open accessible Automotive-related VNFs and NetApp templates, that will form a repository for SMEs to use and develop new applications. Finally, 5G-IANA will develop a Distributed Artificial Intelligence / Machine Learning (AI/ML) (DML) framework, that will provide functionalities for simplified management and orchestration of collections of AI/ML service components and will allow ML-based applications to penetrate the Automotive world, due to its inherent privacy preserving nature. 5G-IANA will be demonstrated through 7 Automotive-related use cases in 2 5G Stand Alone (SA) testbeds. Moving beyond technological challenges, and exploiting input from the demonstration activities, 5G-IANA will perform a multi-stakeholder cost-benefit analysis that will identify and validate market conditions for innovative, yet sustainable business models supporting a long-

term roadmap towards the pan-European deployment of 5G as key advanced Automotive services enabler.

1.2. Purpose of the deliverable

One of the objectives of WP7 is to develop the necessary and impactful brand identity and communication materials and tools for targeted promotion, so as to ensure mainstreaming of project's results to a wide range of stakeholders at all geographical levels and relevant sectors.

This deliverable D7.1 is aimed to be a reference document on brand material and guidelines for the 5G-IANA consortium that enables and maintains the integrity of the project's overall brand identity to ensure a coherent and efficient communication of the project and its results.

1.3. Intended audience

The dissemination level of this document is public, although it is mainly aimed at the consortium members and the European Commission.

2. 5G-IANA BRAND

2.1. Brand and Visual Identity

Our brand and visual identity use a set of graphic elements to easily identify the 5G-IANA project. They represent the first contact the public has with our project. The overall objective is to create a coherent, consistent, and highly recognisable image of the project that supports communication and dissemination activities. This section gives a brief description of how the brand of 5G-IANA project was established.

2.2. The idea behind

A professional designer has been contracted to create the 5G-IANA brand and visual identity. The project's Brand Book developed by this professional designer is available in Annex 1 of this deliverable.

The creation of the 5G-IANA logo is based on and represents the project's content, comprising three key features: text, symbols, and colours.

Figure 1, 5G-IANA logo

2.2.1. Text

The name of the project (5G and IANA acronym) is jointly read, as both words create a unique identity and harmoniously frame the graphic element of the logo. The 5G abbreviation stands out, indicating the significant role of 5G technology in the project. The acronym "Intelligent Automotive Network Applications" uses a clean-cut, modern typography approach.

2.2.2. Symbols

Semi-circular elements represent interconnectivity and visualize highway lanes. The dashed lines in the first semicircle element indicate road traffic separators. The road element, a key component of the project's logo, indicates the automotive aspect of the project.

2.2.3. Colours

The 5G-IANA logo uses two colours: blue and yellow. The colour scheme is both energetic and calm.

Light yellow refers to the intangible brightness of connectivity and creates a strong contrast with the dark blue. Dark blue refers to the colour of the road; choosing a dark shade of blue instead of black was a deliberate choice as blue also creates a sense of security and road security is one of 5G-IANA's main goals.

3. 5G-IANA BRAND GUIDELINES

It is important to ensure that the integrity of our brand and visual identity is always maintained. This section provides precise guidelines to ensure 5G-IANA brand remains coherent and consistent. Applying these guidelines correctly ensures that our messages are always clear and reinforce the character of the 5G-IANA brand.

3.1. Correct use of the project name

5G-IANA stands for “5G for Intelligent Automotive Network Applications”. The project name 5G-IANA should always be written with a hyphen “-”. The 5G-IANA logo, as a graphic, does not include the hyphen and will be used as such.

3.2. 5G-IANA Logo

3.2.1. Colour Palette

3.2.1.1. Main Colours

CMYK colours are used in printing material while RGB colours are used on web applications.

MAIN COLOURS

CMYK = C96 M67 Y38 K22
RGB = R17 G76 B106
#114c6a

CMYK = C0 M15 Y90 K0
RGB = R255 G214 B52
#ffd634

Figure 2, Logo Main Colours

3.2.1.2. Additional Colours

Additional colours palette can be used for layouts and artworks such as website/posters/leaflets etc. in case a small touch of colour contrast is needed. These colours cannot replace the main colour palette or logotype official colours.

Figure 3, Logo Additional Colours

3.2.2. Logo Variations

3.2.2.1. Positive Format (Primary Format)

Primarily the logo should be used on a white background in its positive format for maximum impact and clarity. In cases where this is not feasible, formats in upcoming sections are available for usage.

Figure 4, Logo Positive Format

3.2.2.2. Negative Format

This format of the 5G-IANA logo is only used when placing the logo on an image, a coloured background, or a pattern.

Figure 5, Logo Negative Format

3.2.2.3. BW/Grayscale Formats

These logo variations are meant to be printed in a grayscale or black and white format (i.e., internal memos).

Figure 6, Logo BW Grayscale Format

3.2.3. Logo Usage

The Clear Space zone around the logo has been determined to ensure the proper visibility of the 5G-IANA logotype.

Maintaining the Clear Space zone between the logo and other graphical elements such as typefaces, images, other logos, etc. ensures that the 5G-IANA logo always appears unobstructed and distinctly separate from any other visuals.

To make sure the logo is always clear and legible, a minimum size requirement was determined. However, when using a lower quality printing technique (i.e., screen-printing), the usage of the logo in a larger size is strongly recommended.

LOGOTYPE PRINT minimum size: 22 mm. W X 20 mm. H

LOGOTYPE SCREEN minimum size: 10 px W | 93 px H

Figure 7, Logo Clear Space zone

3.2.4. Logo Improper use

Improper use of the logo includes any of the following:

- Display the 5G-IANA logo only in the formats that are specified in this deliverable.
- The 5G-IANA logo may not appear in any other colours than the Colour Palette section of this deliverable.

- Do not rotate, skew, scale, redraw, alter, or distort the 5G-IANA logo in any way.
- Do not combine the 5G-IANA logo with any other element such as other logos, words, graphics, photos, slogans, or symbols.

Figure 8, Logo Improper Uses

3.2.5. Logo Usage on social media

The logo should be used in a white background.

3.2.5.1. Logo Twitter

Figure 9, Logo Twitter

3.2.5.2. Logo LinkedIn

Figure 10, Logo LinkedIn

3.2.6. Logo Usage on Backgrounds

When placing the logo on an image, colour, or pattern, it is essential that there is enough contrast between the logo and the background. The logo must not be placed on backgrounds that distract from or compete with the logo.

Figure 11, Logo Usage on Backgrounds

3.3. Brand Typography

5G-IANA primary identity typefaces are Gotham and Montserrat fonts families. Replacing the given typefaces with others should not be done under any circumstances.

3.3.1. Gotham family

Gotham family is primarily intended for deliverables and presentations.

Gotham family font

Book	ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
<i>Book Italic</i>	<i>ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ</i> <i>abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz</i>
Light	ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
<i>Light Italic</i>	<i>ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ</i> <i>abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz</i>
Medium	ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
<i>Bold Italic</i>	<i>ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ</i> <i>abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz</i>

Figure 12, Gotham family font

3.3.2. Montserrat family

Montserrat family must be used for communication materials (leaflets, etc.), and in web and media applications wherever this is possible (i.e., at the 5G-IANA website), to retain consistency.

Montserrat fonts family

Regular	ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
<i>Regular Italic</i>	<i>ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ</i> <i>abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz</i>
Light	ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
<i>Light Italic</i>	<i>ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ</i> <i>abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz</i>
Bold	ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
<i>Bold Italic</i>	<i>ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ</i> <i>abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz</i>

Figure 13, Montserrat family font

3.4. Brand templates

A set of templates has been created for the Project's presentations and deliverables releases. In pursuance of a consistent brand identity, the design of the templates is based on 5G-IANA's brand and visual identity. These templates are presented below:

3.4.1. Presentation Template

A presentation template has been created as the only template for 5G-IANA project related presentations, either for internal (with consortium only) or external (with third parties) use.

This template is available in the project's shared collaboration space (Redmine).

Figure 14, Presentation Template

3.4.2. Deliverable Template

A template for deliverables has been created as the only template for writing deliverables. The objective of the template is a consistent and coherent look and formatting of the 5G-IANA deliverables throughout all Work Packages.

This template is available in the project's shared collaboration space (Redmine).

5G IANA	
Dx.x Deliverable's title	
Dissemination level:	Choose an item.
Work package:	WPx
Task:	Tx.y
Deliverable lead:	Organization
Version:	Vx.y
Submission date:	Click here to enter a date.
Due date:	Click here to enter a date.
Partners:	

Partners logos:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016427 www.5g-iana.com

Figure 15, Deliverable Template

3.5. Additional visual elements: EU emblem and funding

Beneficiaries of the EUs Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme have the obligation to explicitly acknowledge that their action has received EU funding. Unless the Commission requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

- (a) display the EU emblem (Figure 16) and

Figure 16, EU emblem

- (b) include the following text: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016427”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

4. CONCLUSION

Deliverable D7.1 - Brand identity and guidelines, is a reference deliverable aimed at providing 5G-IANA Consortium with clear guidelines to ensure that 5G-IANA brand and visual identity are known and correctly used.

The deliverable provided an overview of the current available materials the 5G-IANA Consortium partners are encouraged to use, so as to ensure a consistent promotion of project results as well as the consolidation of the 5G-IANA brand.

Deliverable D7.1 provides the basis for the communication and dissemination strategy of the 5G-IANA project that will be further developed in upcoming deliverables (D7.2 - Communication strategy and plan, D7.4 - Communication tools, and D7.6 - Dissemination plan).

ANNEXES

Annex 1 – 5G-IANA Brand Book

The purpose of this guide is to assist the Consortium in using the 5G-IANA logo correctly and maintaining the integrity of the project's overall brand identity. It is also a useful aid when instructing typographers and other employees to produce branded items, to design and create 5G-IANA communication material.

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Brand Logo

The idea behind

The creation of the 5G-IANA logo is based on and represents the project's content, comprising three key features: text, shapes and colours.

(text) = The name of the project (5G and IANA acronym) is jointly read, as both words create a unique identity and harmoniously frame the graphic element of the logo. The 5G abbreviation stands out, indicating the significant role of 5G technology in the project. The acronym Intelligent Automotive Network Applications uses a clean-cut, modern typography approach.

(symbols) = Semicircular elements represent interconnectivity and visualize highway lanes. The dashed lines in the first semicircle element indicate road traffic separators. The road element, a key component of the project's logo, indicates the automotive aspect of the project.

Logo Elements

Colour

The 5G-IANA logo uses two colours: blue and yellow.

The colour scheme is both energetic and calm. Light yellow / it refers to the intangible “brightness” of connectivity and creates a strong contrast with the dark blue. Dark blue / it refers to the colour of the road; choosing a dark shade of blue instead of black was a deliberate choice as blue also creates a sense of security and road security is one of 5G-IANA’s main goals.

4

Logo Variations

Positive Format

Positive Format (Primary Format)

Primarily the logo should be used on a white background in its positive format for maximum impact and clarity. In cases where this is not feasible, the versions on page 6 are available for usage.

5

Logo Variations

a) Negative Format

This format of the 5G-IANA logo is only used when placing the logo on an image, a colored background or a pattern.

b) BW/Grayscale Formats

These logo variations are meant to be printed in a grayscale or black and white format (i.e. internal memos).

6

Colour Palette

MAIN COLOURS

CMYK = C96 M67 Y38 K22
RGB = R17 G76 B106
#114c6a

CMYK = C0 M15 Y90 K0
RGB = R255 G214 B52
#d631

ADDITIONAL COLOURS

CMYK = C78 M60 Y50 K34
RGB = R57 G73 B95
#391923

CMYK = C40 M24 Y18 K0
RGB = R156 G173 B168
#9CADBC

CMYK = C45 M60 Y90 K45
RGB = R92 G45 B36
#613A52

CMYK = C38 M50 Y70 K16
RGB = R144 G114 B81
#438A81

MAIN and ADDITIONAL COLOURS

CMYK colours are used in printing material
RGB colours are used on web applications

Additional colours palette can be used for layouts and artworks such as website/posters/leaflets e.t.c. in case you need a small touch of colour contrast. These colours cannot replace main colour palette or logotype official colours

7

Logo Usage

The Clear Space zone around the logo has been determined to ensure the proper visibility of the 5G-IANA logotype. Maintaining the Clear Space zone between the logo and other graphical elements such as typefaces, images, other logos, etc. ensures that the 5G-IANA logo always appears unobstructed and distinctly separate from any other visuals.

To make sure the logo is always clear and legible, a minimum size requirement was determined. However, when using a lower quality printing technique (i.e. screenprinting), the usage of the logo in a larger size is strongly recommended.

8

LOGOTYPE PRINT minimum size
22 mm W X 20 mm H

LOGOTYPE SCREEN minimum size
100 px W | 93 px H

Logo Improper use

Display the 5G-IANA logo only in the formats that are specified in this guide. The 5G-IANA logo may not appear in any other colors than the already specified in page 7 of this guide.

Do not rotate, skew, scale, redraw, alter or distort the 5G-IANA logo in any way.

Do not combine the 5G-IANA logo with any other element such as other logos, words, graphics, photos, slogans or symbols.

9

Logo usage on social media

Logo use on social media: the logo should be used in a white background.

10

twitter icon

linkedin icon

Logo usage on backgrounds

When placing the logo on an image, color or pattern, it is essential that there is enough contrast between the logo and the background. The logo must not be placed on backgrounds that distract from or compete with the logo.

11

Must be always used to all communications material and in web and media applications wherever this is possible (i.e. at the 5G-IANA website), to retain consistency. Replacing the given typeface with others should not be done under any circumstances.

12

Typo
gra
phy
BRAND

Gotham family font

Book ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Book Italic ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Light ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Light Italic ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Medium ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Bold Italic ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Montserrat fonts family

Regular ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Regular Italic ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Light ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Light Italic ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Bold ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Bold Italic ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

13

Typo
gra
phy
BRAND

1) For MS templates and publications

HEADING 1
Gotham Black,
18pt black colors

HEADING 2
Gotham bold,
16pt, blue colors
(RGB R37 G60 B126)

HEADING 3
Gotham bold,
14pt, blue colors (RGB R37 G60
B126)

HEADING 4
Gotham bold,
14pt, blue colors (RGB R37 G60
B126)

Body text
Gotham-Book, 11pt, black colors

2) For Website and other web-applications

HEADING 1
Montserrat bold,
18pt black colors

HEADING 2
Montserrat bold,
16pt, blue colors
(RGB R37 G60 B126)

HEADING 3
Montserrat bold,
14pt, blue colors (RGB R37 G60
B126)

HEADING 4
Montserrat bold,
14pt, blue colors (RGB R37 G60
B126)

Body text
Montserrat-Regular, 11pt, black colors

3) For leaflets and other material

HEADING 1
Montserrat bold,
18pt black colors

HEADING 2
Montserrat bold,
16pt, blue colors
(RGB R37 G60 B126)

HEADING 3
Montserrat bold,
14pt, blue colors (RGB R37 G60
B126)

HEADING 4
Montserrat bold,
14pt, blue colors (RGB R37 G60
B126)

Body text
Montserrat-Regular, 11pt, black colors

